

Effect of carbon nanofillers on the mechanical and functional properties of bioderived poly(alkylene furanoate)-based films

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Poly(alkylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate)s

- the most promising **bioderived alternative** to fossil-based poly(alkylene terephthalates) (PATs)
- superior thermo-mechanical and **gas barrier** properties than those of the corresponding PATs
- strong industrial interest: the “sleeping giant” in the world of bioplastics

diol alkyl chain: $n = 2 - 12$

longer diol alkyl chain
higher molecular mobility

- lower T_g and T_m
- faster crystallization
- higher ductility

V. Tsanaktsis et al., *Materials Letters*, **2016**, 178, 64-67.

PAFs @UniTrento DII

Today's presentation:

PDeF + CNTs

PLA/PDoF/rGO

PLA/PDeF/rGO

PLA/PAFs

1. PDeF + CNTs

multi-walled carbon nanotubes

Poly(decamethylene furanoate)/CNTs

→ PDeF + MWCNT (0 – 2 phr)

$T_g = 0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 $T_m = 110\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

→ **Processing:** solution blending + solution casting

neat PDeF

PDeF/CNT 0.25 phr

PDeF/CNT 2 phr

FE-SEM Zeiss Supra 60; cryofracture surfaces

- smoother and more homogeneous fracture surface
- single CNTs: good disentanglement and dispersion

X-Ray diffraction (XRD)

Italstructures IPD3000; Cobalt anode X-Ray source ($\text{Co}_{\text{K}\alpha} = 1.788965 \text{ \AA}$); 40 kV, 20 mA

- **semicrystalline**: sharp Bragg reflections + amorphous halo
- similar to XRD pattern of aromatic–aliphatic polyesters with long methylene chains → **triclinic β -form** assumed
- modeling of the **crystalline, nano(para)crystalline, and amorphous** fractions (Maud Rietveld software) → semi-quantitative evaluation of the crystallinity degree

- increase in **macrocrystalline** fraction at the expense of the nanocrystalline one until 0.5 phr of CNT, opposite trend for higher concentrations
- **Int. ratio (fitting) underestimates X_c** and gives values similar to those measured by DSC

Tensile tests

Increase in crystallinity
+ refinement in microstructure
→ strengthening-toughening effect

Instron 5969; gauge length 50 mm; 10 mm/min.

- **increase in elastic modulus**

+70% with 0.25 phr CNT
+123% with 2 phr CNT

- **increase in tensile strength**

+108% with 0.25 phr CNT
+131% with 2 phr CNT

- **increase in strain at break**

+180% with 0.25 phr CNT

Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA)

TA DMA Q800; tensile mode; 0.05 % strain

- E' increases for CNT nanocomposites, up to 2023 MPa at -50 °C for PDeF-CNT-2 (+93% vs neat PDeF).
- T_g shifted to higher values with CNT addition, indicating CNTs restricted mobility of PDeF amorphous regions
- Height of $\tan \delta$ peak was not significantly affected by CNT content

Increase in strain at break with CNTs attributed to reduced crystallite size rather than increased molecular mobility.

2. PLA/PDoF+ rGO

polylactide

poly(dodecamethylene 2,5-furandicarboxylate)

reduced graphene oxide

PLA/PDoF/rGO nanocomposites

Poly lactide (PLA)

- widely used **biobased** and **biodegradable** biopolymer
- properties depend on the relative fraction of L- and D-lactide
- Commercial PLA: mostly **PLLA** with 2-4 % of D-lactide

- high **elastic modulus** (2-3 GPa)
- good mechanical **strength** (40-60 MPa)
- good **processability**
- high optical **transparency**

- poor **strain at break and toughness**
- high **moisture** sensitivity
- low **gas barrier** properties
- poor UV-shielding properties

PLA/PDoF/rGO nanocomposites

Prepare and characterize nanocomposite films

Polylactide (PLA)

Poly(dodecamethylene furanoate) (PDoF)

Reduced graphene oxide (rGO)

- **PLA + PDoF (10 wt%)** blend
- **rGO (0.25 to 2 phr)** as a **multifunctional** nanofiller

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- Blend compatibility
 - Crystallization kinetics
 - Mechanical properties
 - Antistatic properties
 - Gas barrier properties

Packaging applications

Microstructure

FE-SEM Zeiss Supra 60; cryofracture surfaces

PLA-PDoF10

- immiscible blend
- PDoF spheroidal domains ($2.6 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$)

PLA-PDoF10-rGO0.25

- rGO preferentially distributed in the PDoF domains
- PDoF domains are rougher and smaller ($1.6 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$)
- \uparrow interfacial interaction

Microstructure

FE-SEM Zeiss Supra 60; cryofracture surfaces

- morphological changes in PDoF domains and in the fracture surface with an increase in the rGO concentration
- rGO agglomeration at high concentrations

Sample preparation

1) GO chemical reduction to rGO

3) Solvent casting

Sample	PLA (wt%)	PDoF (wt%)	rGO (phr)
PLA	100	0	0
PLA-rGO0.25	100	0	0.25
PLA-rGO2	100	0	2
PLA-PDoF10	90	10	0

Sample	PLA (wt%)	PDoF (wt%)	rGO (phr)
PLA-PDoF10-rGO0.25	90	10	0.25
PLA-PDoF10-rGO0.5	90	10	0.5
PLA-PDoF10-rGO1	90	10	1
PLA-PDoF10-rGO2	90	10	2

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Mettler Toledo DSC 30 calorimeter; 10 ° C/min; heating/cooling/heating; nitrogen flow 100 ml/min

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

T_g^{PLA} stable \Rightarrow immiscibility

T_c^{PDoF} increases by increasing rGO concentration:
 \Rightarrow rGO promotes PDoF crystallization

Sample	rGO (phr)	T_c^{PDoF} (°C)
PDoF	0	68.5
PLA-PDoF10	0	69.3
PLA-PDoF10-rGO0.25	0.25	82.0
PLA-PDoF10-rGO0.5	0.5	86.3
PLA-PDoF10-rGO1	1	87.7
PLA-PDoF10-rGO2	2	89.7

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

2nd heating scan

- T_{cc}^{PLA} decreases with rGO, especially when *PDoF* is present
- Two peaks in PLA melting

Sample	rGO (phr)	2 nd HS	1 st HS
		X_c^{PLA} (%)	X_c^{PLA} (%)
PLA	0	2.3	41.3
PLA-rGO0.25	0.25	5.2	38.6
PLA-rGO2	2	5.4	36.0
PLA- <i>PDoF</i> 10	0	1.3	35.9
PLA- <i>PDoF</i> 10-rGO0.25	0.25	4.8	32.0
PLA- <i>PDoF</i> 10-rGO0.5	0.5	6.6	34.9
PLA- <i>PDoF</i> 10-rGO1	1	8.5	33.7
PLA- <i>PDoF</i> 10-rGO2	2	6.3	35.0

$$X_c^{PLA} = \frac{\Delta H_m^{PLA} - \Delta H_{cc}^{PLA}}{w \cdot \Delta H_0^{PLA}} \cdot 100$$

→ *PDoF* and rGO **synergistically** improve PLA crystallization

Mechanical properties

Instron 5969; gauge length 50 mm; 10 mm/min.

- PDoF at 10 wt% enhances PLA ductility
- the contribution of rGO is rather modest
- further improvements may be obtained with a lower rGO content (e.g., 0.1 phr)

Gas barrier properties

Gas phase permeation; R.T.; Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (QMS, Balzers QMG 420);
Roilo et al., Surf. Coat. Technol. 2018, 343, 131-137.

- Both **permeability** and **diffusivity** decrease by increasing rGO fraction
- Data for all gases are comparable

⇒ improvement of the gas barrier properties due to:

- **reduced gas mobility** rather than to a decreased gas solubility
- **longer diffusion paths** for gas molecules

Gas barrier properties

Gas phase permeation; R.T.; Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (QMS, Balzers QMG 420);
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Nielsen model for the diffusivity

$$\frac{D}{D_0} = \frac{1}{\tau}$$

D = nanocomposite diffusivity

D_0 = matrix diffusivity

$$\tau = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \alpha \varphi$$

φ = nanofiller volume fraction

α = nanofiller aspect ratio = w / th

Conclusions: 2 main take-home messages

PDeF/CNT

microstructural homogenization provided by CNTs increases toughness

[1] G. Fredi et al., *Polymers*, **2020**, *12*, 2459.

PLA/PDoF/rGO

rGO is a multifunctional nanofiller

[2] G. Fredi et al., *Molecules*, **2021**, *26*, 2398

[3] G. Fredi et al., *Materials*, **2022**, *15*, 1316